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**COMPOSITIONS BASED ON MODIFICATION OF POLYISOPRENE WITH CHLORINATED
POLYISOBUTYLENE. INVESTIGATION OF THE RHEOLOGY OF A MIXTURE OF
CHLORINATED POLYISOBUTYLENE AND POLYISOPRENE AND THE PROPERTIES OF
COMPOSITIONS BASED ON THEM**

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Abstract

Synthetic isoprene rubber is one of the main rubbers in the tire industry and is the only type of synthetic rubbers that is close in structure and properties to natural rubber. Functional groups are added to isoprene rubber-based compositions to increase their cohesive strength, elastic-hysteresis properties, tear resistance, and adhesion to viscose and metal cords. The application of various methods of structuring polyisoprene modified by adding chlorine-containing compounds to polyisoprene seems promising. [1,2,3] Chlorinated polyisobutylene (CHPI), a functional group compound, was studied by adding it to a polyisoprene (İR)-based composition. The effect of the amount of chlorinated polyisobutylene and its functionality on the rheological, elastic-hysteresis, adhesion, etc. properties of polyisoprene and compositions based on it was determined. [4]

Keywords: isoprene rubber, chlorinated polyisobutylene, rheology, IR spectroscopy, composite

Introduction

Binary mixtures were prepared by modifying isoprene rubber with chlorinated polyisobutylene in

different proportions at a temperature of 40-60 °C on a two roll mixer. (Table 1)

Table 1.

IR / CHPI binary mixtures

N	The code of the mixture						
	Components	1N	2N	3N	4N	5N	6N
1	İR	100	98	96	94	92	90
2	CHPI	-	2.0	4.0	6.0	8.0	10.0
	Sum	100	100	100	100	100	100

IR / CHPI binary mixtures are stored at 155 °C for 15 minutes in an IIRT-5 device and dried to constant weight after 20 hours of extraction with CCl_4 .

Infrared spectroscopy analysis of 1N and 3N mixtures was performed and compared to determine the extent to which the functional group (Cl) is located in the matrix. (Figure 1, Figure 3)

Figure 1. Ir spectrum of 1N sample

Figure 2. Ir spectrum of 3N sample

The presence of a number of peaks in the ir spectrum of both samples in the interval corresponding to $2900-3700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates the presence of methylene groups in both samples. In addition, we can see an increase in the intensity of peaks in the spectra of both samples in the range of $1620-1690\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This shows that in both samples there is a double bond $C = C$. In contrast to the non-CHPI (1N) sample, we can see that the mixture containing 4 p.m CHPI (3N) has a peak in the spectrum of 750 cm^{-1} and a change in intensity. This indicates that the sample with the code 3N has a C-Cl bond, ie a deformed chlorine atom.

Experimental part

The velocity of displacement of IR / CHPI binary mixtures at different temperatures ($100-170\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and different pressures ($4.7024-5.1456\text{ Pa}$) was calculated and the dependence diagram of the logarithmic value of the displacement velocity ($\log \gamma$) on the logarithmic value of the displacement pressure ($\log \tau$) was plotted.[6,7]

The logarithmic value ($\log \mathcal{Z}$) of the effective viscosities of alloys of IR / CHPI binary mixtures was calculated. Then a diagram of the dependence of the $\log \mathcal{Z}$ on the was $\log \tau$ constructed. .[5]

After preparing the composition according to the following recipe, it was vulcanized and the physical - mechanical properties of the composition were studied.(Table 2)

Table 2

Recipe of the composition based on IR / CHPI

n	Code of mixtures						
	Components	1N	2N	3N	4N	5N	6N
1	IR	100	98	96	94	92	90
2	CHPI	-	2	4	6	8	10
3	Stearic acid	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
4	Oleic acid	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
5	Rosin	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
6	ZnO	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
7	Neozone (D)	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
8	santoflex	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
9	N-nitroso dyphenylamine	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7
10	Rubrax	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
11	Modifier RU-1	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
12	Captax	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
13	Sulfonamide 15	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2
14	Microvosk	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
15	Carbon black P-514	45	45	45	45	45	45
16	Sulfur	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
	SUM	167.2	167.2	167.2	167.2	167.2	167.2

Results and its discussions

At 100 and $120\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, when analyzing the displacement pressure dependence diagram of the displacement velocity, we see that the displacement velocity of the alloys of binary mixtures is two times higher than that of polyisoprene and increases sharply under the influence of pressures of 4.7024 and 4.9515 Pa . Under the

influence of subsequent pressures (5.0488 and 5.1456 Pa), it increases relatively little.(Figure 3, Figure 4)

In the IR / CHPI mixture, the dependence on the amount of CHPI varies very little. Even when the amount of CHPI in the mixture is $6-10\text{ p.m}$, the displacement velocities of the alloys overlap.It can be concluded that when the amount of CHPI in the IR / CHPI

mixture is 2-6 p.m and the pressure acting on the alloy is a maximum of 4.9515 Pa, the interaction of CHPI with IR is maximal and then decreases relatively. That

is, the mixture can be processed under a maximum pressure of 4.9515 Pa.

Figure 3. Dependence of displacement rate on displacement pressure at 100°C

Figure 4. Dependence of displacement rate on displacement pressure at 120°C

At a temperature of 150°C, the displacement velocities of the alloys of IR / CHPI binary mixtures overlap at all pressures. In the range of 4.7024-4.6515 Pa, it increases sharply. (Figure 5) With the subsequent increase in pressure, the rate of displacement increases significantly. It is reaffirmed that the amount of CHPI

in the mixture should be between 2-6 p.m and processing should be carried out under the influence of pressure 4.7024-4.9515 Pa. Under higher pressure, the system undergoes severe destruction.

Figure 5. Dependence of displacement rate on displacement pressure at 150°C

At a temperature of 178 ° C, the displacement velocities of the alloys of IR and IR / CHPI binary mixtures under the influence of all pressures are very close to each other and the velocity is large. This indicates that the system is undergoing rapid destruction. (Figure 6)

Figure 6. Dependence of displacement speed on displacement pressure at 178°C

The effective viscosities ($\log \eta$) of IR / CHPI binary mixtures at temperatures of 150-178 ° C, were studied and the dependence of $\log \eta$ on $\log \tau$ was constructed. (Figure 7-10)

Figure 7. Dependence of effective viscosity on displacement pressure at 100°C

Figure 8. Dependence of effective viscosity on displacement pressure at 120°C

Figure 9. Dependence of effective viscosity on displacement pressure at 150°C

Figure 10. Dependence of effective viscosity on displacement pressure at 178°C

This research once again confirms that binary mixtures can be processed at temperatures below 100 °C and under the influence of low pressures, and the composition based on it can be vulcanized at 155 °C. Rheological research shows that at temperatures above 150 °C, the flow of the binary mixture first increases and after 15 minutes begins to decrease. That is, in the macromolecule of polyisoprene, structuring occurs (ie, vulcanization occurs) and the flow begins to decrease.

According to the recipe shown in Table 2, the composition was prepared by modifying polyisoprene (IR) with chlorinated polyisobutylene (CHPI) in different proportions. The composition based on IR / CHPI was prepared at a temperature of 40-50 °C for 40 minutes. The prepared composition was vulcanized at 155 °C for 15 minutes. The physical and mechanical properties of the vulcanizates of the compositions based on IR / CHPI were studied and given in Table 3.

Table 2

Recipe of the composition based on IR / CHPI

n	Properties		Code of mixtures						
			1N	2N	3N	4N	5N	6N	
1	Tensile strength at break MPa		20.2	20.4	21.1	20.6	19.9	19.2	
2	100% elongation strength, MPa		2.0	2.2	2.9	3.1	3.3	3.2	
3	300% elongation strength, MPa		8.6	8.7	9.1	9.7	9.9	9.0	
4	Relative stretch, %		530	535	540	535	528	520	
5	Relative residual deformation, %		25	25	25.1	24.9	24.6	24	
6	Tear resistance, kN/m		62.3	63.4	64.8	65.7	65.1	64	
7	Elasticity on the back leap, %		41.5	42	41.8	41.6	41	39	
8	Hardness by TM-2 device, c.u		58.3	58	59	59.5	59.8	60.1	
9	Coefficients of aging from heat at 373 K temperature for 70 hours,%	ϵ_1	0.45	0.47	0.52	0.58	0.60	0.62	
		ϵ_2	0.39	0.40	0.41	0.40	0.39	0.38	
10	Coefficient of fatigue tolerance under repeated deformation($t=273K, v = \text{period}/\text{min}$)		8.5	8.6	8.9	8.7	7.6	7	
11	contact strength(adhesion)	Strength of cord connection by H method, $kN * 10^{-2}$	296 K	3.8	4.7	5	5.8	6.2	6.3
			373 K	3.3	4.5	4.8	5.2	5.8	5.8
		Metal contact strength, MPa	2.3	3.2	3.9	4.5	4.9	5	

The analysis of the properties of vulcanizates shows that the properties of the composition based on IR / CHPI (2-6 p.m) have improved compared to the properties of the composition (standard) based on IR: At 100 and 300% elongation, the conditional stresses increased from 2.0 and 8.6 MPa to 3.3 and 9.7 MPa, respectively, the tear resistance increased from 62.3 kN/m to 65.7 kN/m, the thermal aging increased from 0.45 to 0.58, and the cord strength increased from 2.3 to 4.5.

A composite based on IR (98-94) / CHPI (2-6) can be considered an optimal system. As a result, IR / CHPI-based composite can be used in the rubber industry for the production of carcasses (body parts) and conveyor belts.

References

1. Вилалов.Й.М.,Мовлаев И.Г.,Мамедов.Ф.В.,Ибрагимов.А.Д.,Свойства резин на основе изопренового каучука и хлорполимеров, Химия и химическая технология,1986, С.121-124
2. Курбанова Н.И., Ищенко Н.Я., Трифель Б.Ю.Влияние модификации бинарных смесей дивинилового и изопренового каучуков на свойства композиций. Пластические массы.2006. Номер.4. С.17-19

3. Mahmoud Kardan; Adhesive and Cohesive Strength in Polyisoprene/Polychloroprene Blends. Rubber Chemistry and Technology, 2001; 74 (4): 614–621

4. Ignatenko, VY, Kostyuk, AV, Smirnova, NM, Antonov, SV, Ilyin, SO. Asphaltenes as a tackifier for hot-melt adhesives based on the styrene-isoprene-styrene block copolymer. Polym Eng Sci. 2020; 60: 2224– 2234.

5. İ.H.Mövlayev, S.M.İbrahimova, G.M.Məmmədova, G.R.Qızıyeva, D.N.Cəfərova.Poliizoprenlə modifikasiya olunmuş bitumun və onun əsasında örtüklərin xassələrinin tədqiqi.Azərbaycan Dövlət Neft və Sənaye universiteti.Azərbaycan kimya jurnalı № 2. 2014.səh(65-70)

6. J. A. Waterman, G. E. la Heij, H. van Hoorn Grafting of methyl methacrylate on isoprene rubber. Journal of Applied Chemistry .2007.17(5):121 – 125

7. Билалов Я.М.О., Мовлаев И.Г.О., Ибрагимова С.М.Г., Бабаева Р.Э.Г.Модификация резиновой смеси на основе изопренового и бутадиен-стирольного каучуков хлорированным атактическим полипропиленом. Промышленное производство и использование эластомеров.2010. Номер 1.С.23-24